

Sustain Sahel

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Deliverable 8.2 Videos for Farmers

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1. Executive summary

Up to the current project phase, two main activities are led by Access Agriculture in the framework of the project: The translation of existing videos and the production of new project videos. The aim of the current deliverable is, according to the project proposal, to report on the selection and translation of existing videos into the languages spoken on SustainSahel’s 7 sites and disseminate them to farmers. More details regarding the production of new videos will be given in deliverables D8.3 and D8.4.

So far, 23 translations of videos were completed and uploaded on platforms and shared with project partners for use. Additionally, 10 new translations of videos produced by a project collaborator (not previewed in the project proposal) are being carried out by Access Agriculture.

Regarding the production of new videos, Access Agriculture has started the process. Four videos are expected to be produced by Access Agriculture in the framework of the project, showcasing the innovations tested and validated by SustainSahel. From these, one video on ‘Mulching with trees and shrubs for a better crop’ is on advanced stage and will be finalized in the second quarter of 2024. The remaining three videos are still in the first stages of conceptualization and/or planning.

2. Video translation and production

2.1 Translation of videos

In the proposal, 15 existing videos were supposed to be selected and translate into 9 languages by M40.

After a careful visualization and evaluation of existing videos on farmers practices related with crop-shrub-livestock integration, the project partners have co-selected 9 videos, considered relevant for their target regions. 5 Languages were relevant for the 3 countries: Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof, and Serer.

For Burkina Faso, 4 videos were translated into Mooré, 2 videos into Bambara for Mali, 4 videos into Wolof, 4 into Fulani, and 9 into Serer for Senegal.

In sum, 23 videos translations were done for the project as shown in the Table 2.1 below

All the translated videos were uploaded on Access Agriculture website and accessible for anyone in the project countries to watch and to download them. The links are provided in Appendix.

Videos	Existing languages	Translations done
Managed Regeneration	Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof	Serer
Animals and trees for a better crop	Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof	Serer
Parkland agroforestry	Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof	Serer
Farmers and pastoralists	Bambara, Fulani, Wolof	Mooré, Serer
Enriching porridge with Baobab juice		Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof, Serer

Videos	Existing languages	Translations done
Mulch for a better soil and crop	Bambara, Mooré	Fulani, Wolof, Serer
Herbal treatment for diarrhea		Bambara, Mooré, Fulani, Wolof, Serer
Keeping sheep healthy	Bambara, Mooré	Fulani, Wolof, Serer
Living windbreaks to protect the soil	Bambara, Fulani, Wolof	Mooré, Serer

Table 2-1. List of videos translated and languages

2.2. Production of new project videos

During the annual meeting of 2023 in Ouagadougou, Burkina Faso, the project partners have collectively suggested 25 technologies as potential topics for the production of new videos. Producing a single video requires skills, time, and availability of experts to comment the various versions of scripts. After evaluation of the 25 technologies, four topics were finally retained for video production: Use of indigenous bush biomass for mulch (*Guiera senegalensis*, *Piliostigma reticulatum*)- Alley cropping with *Gliricidia sepium* and *Leucaena leucocephala* - Antihelminthic treatments for small ruminants and interaction with wild fodder - Optimal density of bushes and trees.

The first video on Bush biomass and Mulching is ongoing as described in section 2.2.1.

2.2.1 Video on ‘the use of indigenous bush biomass for mulch’

Video production has 5 main steps: Script – Pre filming – Filming – Initial edit – Final edit.

For this first video, we have developed the script and received comments from experts and local partners of the project. The script was finalized with inputs of partners. A team was sent to Burkina Faso and has visited fields and 2 villages for the pre-filming and the filming. Footages were collected for the initial edit.

Unfortunately, due to the topic selection process and the time spent for writing and validating the script by project partners, the filming team missed the beginning of the agricultural season and was therefore unable to complete the video in 2023. To ensure the quality of the video, Access Agriculture has decided to hold on till the next season in order to have a complete and illustrative video that will be suitable for training purposes. Once the footage is obtained, the video will be finished early Q2 of 2024

Photos: Filming in Saria (photos courtesy of Michel Kaba)

2.2.2 Production, translation and dubbing of two new videos based on SustainSahel's new illustrations

As an extra activity not previewed in the project proposal, two new videos have been produced by project collaborator Lilian Beck (University of Hohenheim), based on the new illustrations produced for the project brochure portraying the advantages of agroforestry in the Sahelian context. The videos have been uploaded on YouTube on the 15th of November. The videos have been released in French in order to be suitable for broader dissemination in the three project countries, and are currently being translated and dubbed into the 5 project site languages mentioned above: Wolof, Fulani, Serer, Mooré and Bambara by Access Agriculture.

The two extra videos are:

- An example of an agroforestry farm in the Sahel: <https://youtu.be/WzABL5uK8cU?si=PI96FlciwIGCAOga>
- Advantages of agroforestry for the Sahel: <https://youtu.be/FjEMhY-1IEY?si=IO0Wg7bUBiD0k5de>

Captions of the videos from SustainSahel's YouTube channel.

3. Dissemination activities related with the Deliverable

3.1 Upload of the videos on Access Agriculture video platform and viewing data

All the above translated videos are freely downloadable from the Access Agriculture video platform. Likewise, related farmer-friendly factsheets and audio files are accessible from the platform after registration at www.accessagriculture.org. The videos will be linked to the project's own website and social media channels.

The table 2.1 presents an overview of the viewing data about the 9 videos translated for SustainSahel.

Viewing data across SustainSahel languages including French and English for the period of 1st May 2022 to 13 December 2023				
Video titles	Video downloads	Video online views	Audio downloads	Document downloads
Herbal treatment for diarrhoea	158	949	2	79
Enriching porridge with baobab juice	120	262	3	37
Keeping sheep healthy	201	327	1	31
Mulch for a better soil and crop	613	7,251	15	174
SLM11 Farmers & pastoralists	88	40	2	28
Living windbreaks to protect the soil	63	123	0	26
Animals & trees for a better crop	111	36	6	38
SLM08 Parkland agroforestry	81	71	4	39
SLM10 Managed regeneration	80	65	0	23
TOTAL	1,515	9,124	33	475

Table 2-2. Viewing data

In total, visitors of the website have downloaded 1,515 video versions. 9,124 people have viewed the video online. We also noticed 33 audio files, useful for media, were downloaded and 475 downloads of video factsheets.

In addition, the translated videos were added to the library of our teams of young entrepreneurs who organised some video shows in Sahel countries to enable farmers to learn new practices.

3.2 Dissemination of the videos to the 200 project lead farmers in mini-SD memory cards

The 9 videos were uploaded in mini-SD memory cards for cell-phones that were distributed to each of the 200 lead farmers, a task that was locally carried out by CSE (Centre de Suivi Écologique, Dakar, Senegal). The decision to use the video on mobile-phone approach is related to the fact that all lead farmers either have a mobile phone compatible with the use of mini-SD memory cards or have at least one household member who has it. Farmers in the intervention areas have the habit of watching videos on their mobile phones for entertainment or learning, which makes this learning tool well adapted to the local context. Furthermore, sharing the videos with farmers in this way enables them to become the disseminators of the videos themselves, since most of them have the habit to share the videos they like with their peers via the costless Bluetooth technology.

The mini-SD cards were shared with farmers in the second open field day events of 2022 and by the beginning of 2023 in case of Sikasso. In total, 200 mini-SD memory cards were distributed to farmers, with 60 in Senegal (Fulani, Serer and Wolof versions), 60 in Mali (Bambara versions) and 80 in Burkina Faso (Mooré versions).

A short questionnaire to address farmers' perceptions and preferences regarding the shared videos was integrated in the socio-economic profile survey to be carried out by farmers' organizations with all lead farmers and is expected to generate insights for future dissemination activities.

4. Appendix I

List of videos translated and links to access

4.1 Wolof

1. Herbal treatment for diarrhoea:
2. Enriching porridge with baobab juice: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22364>
3. Keeping sheep healthy: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22363>
4. Mulch for a better soil and crop: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22367>

4.2 Fulani

5. Herbal treatment for diarrhoea: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22352>
6. Enriching porridge with baobab juice: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22353>
7. Keeping sheep healthy: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22351>
8. Mulch for a better soil and crop: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22350>

4.3 Mooré

9. SLMII Farmers & pastoralists: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22300>
10. Living windbreaks to protect the soil: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22303>
11. Herbal treatment for diarrhoea: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22301>
12. Enriching porridge with baobab juice: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22302>

4.4 Bambara

13. Herbal treatment for diarrhoea: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22272>
14. Enriching porridge with baobab juice: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22273>

4.5 Serer

15. Herbal treatment for diarrhoea: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22427>
16. Enriching porridge with baobab juice: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22501>
17. Keeping sheep healthy: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22499>
18. Mulch for a better soil and crop: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22494>
19. Animals & trees for a better crop: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22423>
20. SLM08 Parkland agroforestry: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22424>
21. SLM10 Managed regeneration: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22425>
22. SLMII Farmers & pastoralists: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22426>
23. Living windbreaks to protect the soil: <https://www.accessagriculture.org/node/22495>

Deliverable 8.2 Videos for Farmers

<h3>Enriching porridge with Baobab juice</h3>		<p>Current language Bambara</p> <p>Available languages Arabic, Alban, Bambara, Chichewa/Nyanja, English, French, Kiswahili, Malagasy, Mooré, Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar, Portuguese, Serer, Spanish, Wolof</p> <p>Need a language? If you would like this video translated into other languages, please contact kevin@accessagriculture.org</p> <p>Translated in Mali</p> <p>Translation funded by Sustain Sahel</p> <p>Uploaded 1 year ago</p> <p>Duration 7:54</p> <p>Produced by Hochschule Rhein-Waal, Blousson</p> <p>Share Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, E-mail</p> <p>Categories Cereals > Maize Fruits & Nuts > Other fruits Other > Nutrition</p>
<h3>Mulch for a better soil and crop</h3>		<p>Current language Wolof</p> <p>Available languages Arabic, Bambara, Bangla, Bemba, Chichewa/Nyanja, Chitonga/Tonga, English, Fon, French, Ibibio, Igbo, Kinyarwanda/Kirundi, Kiswahili, Luganda, Marathi, Mooré, Nyanjalingang/Komangang, Persian/Farsi, Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar, Portuguese, Sereer, Sinhala, Spanish, Telugu, Tumbuka, Wolof</p> <p>Need a language? If you would like this video translated into other languages, please contact kevin@accessagriculture.org</p> <p>Translated in SENEGAL</p> <p>Translation funded by Sustain Sahel</p> <p>Uploaded 1 year ago</p> <p>Duration 1:35</p> <p>Produced by Atul Pagar, WOTR</p> <p>Share Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, E-mail</p> <p>Categories Vegetables > Other vegetables Fruits & Nuts > Other fruits Sustainable Land Management > Agroforestry, Soil fertility management Other > Climate change adaptation</p>
<h3>Herbal treatment for diarrhoea</h3>		<p>Current language Mooré</p> <p>Available languages Arabic, Aneko, Bambara, Bangla, Chichewa/Nyanja, English, Fon, French, Fulfulde (Comoros), Chomaria, Hindi, Kannada, Kinyarwanda/Kirundi, Luganda, Malagasy, Marathi, Mooré, Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar, Serer, Spanish, Telugu, Wolof</p> <p>Need a language? If you would like this video translated into other languages, please contact kevin@accessagriculture.org</p> <p>Translated in Burkina Faso</p> <p>Translation funded by Sustain Sahel</p> <p>Uploaded 1 year ago</p> <p>Duration 9:53</p> <p>Produced by Atul Pagar, ANTHRA</p> <p>Share Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, E-mail</p> <p>Categories Livestock > Animal health, Sheep & Goats</p>
<h3>Keeping sheep healthy</h3>		<p>Current language Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar</p> <p>Available languages Arabic, Bambara, Bangla, Barba, Burmese, Chichewa/Nyanja, Chitonga/Tonga, English, French, Ghomari, Hausa, Hindi, Karam / Karoum, Mooré, Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar, Portuguese, Serer, Spanish, Telugu, Wolof</p> <p>Need a language? If you would like this video translated into other languages, please contact kevin@accessagriculture.org</p> <p>Translated in SENEGAL</p> <p>Translation funded by Sustain Sahel</p> <p>Uploaded 1 year ago</p> <p>Duration 12:48</p> <p>Produced by AMEDD</p> <p>Share Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, E-mail</p> <p>Categories Livestock > Animal health, Sheep & Goats Sustainable Land Management > Integrated crop-livestock, Pastoralism & Rangelands</p>
<h3>Living windbreaks to protect the soil</h3>		<p>Current language Mooré</p> <p>Available languages Arabic, Aramaic, Bambara, English, French, Kannada, Kiswahili, Luganda, Mooré, Peulh / Fulfulde / Pulaar, Quechua, Serer, Spanish, Wolof</p> <p>Need a language? If you would like this video translated into other languages, please contact kevin@accessagriculture.org</p> <p>Translated in Burkina Faso</p> <p>Translation funded by Sustain Sahel</p> <p>Uploaded 1 year ago</p> <p>Duration 15:00</p> <p>Produced by Agro-insight</p> <p>Share Facebook, Twitter, LinkedIn, E-mail</p> <p>Categories Other Crops > Other crops Sustainable Land Management > Other SLM Other > Biodiversity conservation, Climate change adaptation</p>